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A NORMATIVE DISCOURSE ON THE PROS AND CONS OF NEW EDUCATION POLICY 2020

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Abstract

The purpose of Education should be gauged in its ability to inculcate morals, value system and skill set among the learners so as to make them an asset for the nation. Human Capital formation is going to play a very important role in development of the nation. The nation's education system has largely remained unchanged since last 3 decades. It is to be noted that, that advent of Information communication technology which has paved way to knowledge economy has disrupted the ways in which how things are taught, how things are learnt and how things are done. In this context, to ensure our youth are endowed with skill set relevant for 21st century, revamping our education system was the need of the hour. This paper analyses the evolution of National Education Policy and the relevance of latest upgradation in meeting the needs and aspirations of young India.

Keywords: Education system, disruption, Human Capital Formation, National Education Policy, Disruption, Knowledge Economy, Relevance

Introduction: National Education policy 2020 has been implemented with the aim of revamping the prevailing education system in order to make education relevant to the changing needs and aspirations of present youth (Kurien, et al 2020). Before dwelling upon the pros and cons of new education Policy and its significance in meeting the dynamic changes that India is going to be facing in contemporary times, it becomes pertinent for us to understand the nature and structure of Indian Education system. In this backdrop the objective of the paper is to trace evolution of previous NEPs and to analyse how useful and novel the initiative envisaged by New Education Policy is going to be in helping India tread a path of inclusive development in modern times.

Evolution of Education in India post-Independence: Given the socio-economic and political turmoil amidst which our nation got her independence, our leadership wanted to preserve unity and integrity of nation along with creating a conducive environment which could facilitate upward social mobility of masses. Our national leadership had realised the importance of providing quality education for the masses from the very beginning. To achieve the same, under

the guidance of eminent leaders and thinkers various commissions and committees were established. To truly understand the novelty of present National Education Policy (2020), it becomes pertinent for us to have a brief understanding of the prominent policies which came before.

First and foremost, under the able leadership of Dr S Radhakrishnan (1948), University Education commission was formed which sought to strengthen the structure of university to meet the changing demands of a young nation (Panditrao & Panditrao, 2020). The most prominent recommendation of this commission resulted in reconstituting University Grants Commission in the same lines as that of United Kingdom’s University Grants Committee. The base which was laid by the first commission was to be strengthened further by Kothari Commission which was formed in 1966 which was headed by Daulat Singh Kothari, the then Chairman of University Grants Commission. Kothari commission wanted to ensure that Indian Education system would be in a position of competing with the best. To ensure that no stone was left unturned, eminent academicians and leaders like Director of UNESCO, Professors of Harvard University, members of London school of economics were consulted. Unlike the first commission which was formed to give guidelines on how universities must be structured, Kothari Commission sort to work out a framework to cover all the possible dimensions which could improve the quality of education (Kalyani, P. 2020). To achieve the same various task forces were constituted which ranged from Adult Education, Agricultural education, Educational Finance, Higher Education, Teacher Education, working group on educational buildings, Working group on women’s education, Task force on Vocational and Technical education, Task force on Teacher education and Teacher Status and the like. The varied dimension covered by the task force reflected the magnitude of change which Kothari commission wanted to bring forth in the framework of nation’s education. It was Kothari Commission which recommended standardisation of education system in 10+2+3 pattern. The commission classified Montessori, Kindergarten as pre-primary and upto 4th standard as lower primary, 5th to 8th standard as Higher primary, 9th and 10th standard as lower secondary and 11th and 12th standard as Higher secondary. The Curriculum prescribed by the commission has been summarised in table 1.

Table 1: School Curriculum as Prescribed by Kothari Commission

Lower Primary Level (1 to 4)	
One Language	Creative Studies
Mathematical studies	Health Studies
Environmental Studies	Work Experience
Higher Primary (5 to 8)	
Two Languages (One Regional and One National) and preferably a third language	Art
Mathematical studies	Physical Education

Science Studies	Work experience
Social studies	Moral Studies
Lower Secondary Level (9 and 10)	
Three Languages	Art
Mathematical Studies	Physical education
Science Studies	Work experience
Social Studies	Moral Studies
Higher Secondary Level (11 and 12)	
Two Languages (One Modern Indian Language and One Classical or Foreign Language)	Art
	Physical education
Any three subjects from one Additional Language, and 2 subjects belonging to either Arts stream or Science Stream.	Work experience
	Moral Studies

Other prominent recommendations of the commission were to establish guidance and counselling centres for students. The commission also suggested to implement a new system of evaluation for assessing students' performance in lines of continuous comprehensive evaluation. Furthermore, the commission suggested to establish Indian Education Service to inculcate professional management in Education Sector. The said service was to be modelled along the lines of Indian Administrative Service. Pay scale of teachers were to be enhanced along with establishment of a machinery for continuous on the job training for teaching staff. Most importantly, the Commission suggested to raise educational expenditure to 6 percent of GDP. Thus, we can see that Kothari Commission had laid a comprehensive framework for formalisation of education and making it relevant to meet the needs and demands of the time.

In 1986, new National Policy on Education was introduced by Government led by the then Premier Rajiv Gandhi. The time was nearly 3 decades after independence. A new air of confidence was emerging in the nation. Keeping with the times and wanting to expand on the foundation laid by its predecessors, the National Policy on Education (1986) gave "special emphasis on the removal of disparities and to equalise educational opportunity". The focus of the policy was to empower women, people belonging to scheduled caste and scheduled tribe who were hitherto deprived of getting education due to social construct and discrimination. To ensure affordable education was provided to all, the policy gave emphasis on expanding upon open university system which was initiated with the creation of Indira Gandhi National Open University in 1985. To promote social and economic development at the grassroots level, National Education Policy also gave emphasis on creation of "rural university" model.

In 1992 National Education policy (1986) was modified by the then premier P.V. Narsimha Rao. The modification was made to keep up with changing times. After undergoing a financial crisis, the nation had adopted a new policy of liberalization, privatization and globalisation. It needed skilled human capital to help the economy recover and drive it to greater heights. To ensure quality in education, the modification sought to introduce common entrance examination on all India basis for admission to professional and technical programmes in the country. As of 2001, government of India, has laid down a three-exam scheme. Joint Entrance Examination (JEE) and All India Engineering Entrance Exam (AIEEE) are entrance exams to be conducted at National level for entrance into national level institutions. State Level Engineering Entrance Examinations (SLEEE) are held for State level institutions with an option to join AIEEE. Although it was a well thought out initiative, more often than not, students started preparing for all the exams hoping to clear at least one and started falling prey for unwarranted stress. All in all, the initiative of the policy to instil a system in place to ensure quality was definitely a step in right direction. Another significant development which happened after National Education Policy 1986/92, has been the implementation of Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act 2009 which laid down legal safeguards for universal education.

21st century has been the harbinger of digital age. It has revolutionised the way people learn and work. In west, information communication technology has long been leveraged to enhance the effectiveness and efficacy of learning system. In a world where in we are generating roughly 2.5 quintillion bytes of data everyday (Dobbins et al., 2014) and data is regarded as new oil, there is a genuine need for revamping the present education system to make our youth relevant and employable in changing scenario.

In keeping with changing times to modernise Indian Education system, a panel was formed under the visionary leadership of former ISRO chief Krishnaswamy Kasturirangan which submitted the draft NEP in 2019. Later, Ministry of Human Resource Development augmented the policy framework by undertaking a rigorous consultation process through which it took over 2 lakh suggestions from Gram Panchayats and Urban Local Bodies of 676 districts.

The prominent features of the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 are as follows (GoI, 2020):

1. Measures to enhance Learning Experience among Students: Life is not just to be endured; life is to be enjoyed as well. Same principle can very well be applied for education. NEP 2020 tries to bring in structural changes which are designed to make learning experience more wholistic, relevant and fun. The structural changes envisaged by NEP to achieve the same are summarised in Table2:

Table 2. Structural Changes Designed to enhance Learning Experience among Students

Changing the Pedagogical structure	With an objective of making the pedagogical structure of the school education responsive and relevant to the learner's needs 10+2+3 design is to be replaced with 5+3+3+4 design.
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Focus on wholistic development of Learners	<p>NEP recognises that the aim of education cannot be just cognitive development, but its focus must lie on imparting 21st century relevant skills and knowledge among learners. Moreover, the policy underlies the fact that all students may not have academic inclination. To accommodate varied and diverse interests, NEP tries to integrate arts and sports to academic curricula in a balanced manner.</p> <p>Interestingly, NEP also recognises the importance of specialisation and competition in sports. To facilitate the students who are genuinely interested to pursue sports, arts and career NEP has proposed to introduce “BAL BHAWAN”, a special boarding school which is to be established in every district to formally train students who are genuinely interested in pursuing a career in arts and sports.</p>
Experimental Learning	<p>The emphasis of education system as envisaged by NEP is not necessarily to teach students something. The emphasis is on teaching students how to learn something. Latter approach is designed to enable students to be lifelong learners thereby making them stay ever relevant in their chosen endeavour.</p>
Promotion of Critical Thinking	<p>NEP wants to shift the focus from teacher centric approach to student centric approach. The focus is less on “how much you learnt” and more on “how can you apply what you have learnt”. The objective is to create a cohort of learners who are adept at problem solving and decision making. In no way NEP ignores the importance of theory, but it tries to give greater importance on application of concepts rather than making the student just know about the concept. By doing so NEP envisages to create a classroom which is more, engaging, entertaining, and enlightening to all the actors concerned.</p>
Flexibility in Course Choices	<p>In the existing structure, students are streamlined to take up either science, arts or commerce subjects at pre university level. To achieve its objective of wholistic development, NEP has removed hard bound separation among ‘curricular’, ‘extracurricular’ or between ‘arts’, ‘humanities and ‘science’ or between ‘vocational’ and ‘academic’ streams. The new framework is designed to incorporate subjects like ‘physical education’, ‘arts and crafts’, ‘vocational skills’ in addition to ‘science’ and ‘humanities’, by taking into account the interest and safety of learners.</p>
Emphasis on Multilingualism	<p>NEP recognises that young children who are starting their journey of learning will be more adept in grasping things if they are taught in their respective mother tongue. Recognising this and to facilitate easier learning among the young cohort,</p>

	<p>medium of instruction is to be one's mother tongue till class 5 and preferably up to class 8.</p> <p>At the same point of time, NEP understands the need to facilitate the ambitions and aspirations of parents and children. To accommodate the aspirations of people, regions and Union in keeping with constitutional provisions, implementation of three language formula is allowed to continue without any disruption. However, there are certain safeguards in implementing the same:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">i) No language shall be imposed on any state.ii) Of the three languages which is to be learnt by the students, two must be native to India.iii) Students who wish to change one or more of the three languages may do so in Grade 6 or 7, provided they display basic proficiency in the three languages. <p>In addition to these, to inculcate a spirit of appreciation for linguistic diversity which is present in India, active encouragement shall be given to the educational institutions to design programmes through which students could get familiarity with Indian Classical Languages.</p> <p>To build a sense of cultural awareness among the students at both national and international level, students will have the option of learning at least two years of classical language of India.</p> <p>If on the other hand, students are interested in learning foreign languages like French, Spanish, Portuguese, Russian, Korean, Japanese and the like, they would be able to do so at secondary level.</p>
Transforming Assessment for Student Development	<p>NEP focuses on shifting assessment of students based on exams which gives emphasis on rote learning to multi-dimensional wholistic assessment which tries to assess the progress of learner in the cognitive, affective and psychomotor domains.</p> <p>Previous system of Board Exam for Classes 10 and 12 shall continue to prevail. However, the design of assessment is going to be radically different.</p> <p>To ensure that students don't fall prey to rote learning and coaching institutes, board exams shall be designed in such a manner that they test the core competencies of students which would not require rote learning. Moreover, to reduce the stress</p>

	<p>of “high stakes” in board exams, students will be allowed to take the board exam on up to two occasions during any given school year. One would be main examination and the other would be for improvement, if desired.</p> <p>To further ensure that there is continuous assessment of student throughout the school years and not just at 10th and 12th standard, school examinations in classes 3, 5 and 8 shall be conducted by appropriate authority to test the efficacy of basic learning outcomes.</p> <p>NEP envisages to set up a National Assessment Centre, PARAKH (Performance Assessment, Review, and Analysis of Knowledge for Holistic development) which shall be instituted under Ministry of Human resource and Development. The institution shall undertake State Achievement Survey and National Achievement Survey to monitor learning outcomes of the nation.</p> <p>Moreover, this Institution shall also advise the School Boards regarding new assessment patterns and promote a culture of collaboration among the School Boards. This shall play a important role in ensuring equivalence of academic standards across the board.</p> <p>The guiding principles for University Entrance Exams are not subjected to any radical change. However, as opposed to the prevailing system in which there are hundreds of universities devising their own entrance exam, the responsibility of conducting one common entrance exam shall be given to National Testing Agency (NTA). It will serve as a premier autonomous body which shall conduct entrance exam for admission of students in graduate, post graduate and fellowships for doctoral studies in Higher Educational Institutions.</p>
<p>Assistance for Gifted Students</p>	<p>NEP recognises that some students may excel in unique fields which may not be part of the curriculum. It may range from dance, drama, music, yoga, sports, poetry, maths and so on.</p> <p>To ensure that justice is done to the genuine interests of the students across fields beyond syllabus, NEP envisages active encouragement and promotion of Literary Clubs, Chess Circles, Poetry Circles, Drama Circles, Debate Circles, Sports Circles and the like within school premises.</p>

	<p>In addition to that NEP envisages to arrange national level competitions and Olympiads to develop a spirit of competition and sportsmanship among students</p>
<p>Vocational Training</p>	<p>In present societal setup, vocational training has a stigma attached to it (Aldossari, 2020; Essel et al, 2014). It is viewed as a course opted by those students who couldn't excel in formal education. By making vocational training implicit in curriculum, NEP has done a commendable job of removing the stigma.</p> <p>For instance, Many scholars (Wu, Xueping & Ye, Yiqun. 2018) have attributed China's emergence as a manufacturing hub of the world to the great emphasis China has given on imparting vocational education through formal setup. In fact, in China two-thirds of senior secondary curriculum is dedicated to skill based vocational education (Deccan Chronicle, 2020). Southeast Asian Nations who have promoted skill based vocational education have accelerated their Industrial Growth and Development. For instance, second wave of industrial revolution which unfolded in Singapore is largely credited to Singapore's focus on designing and implementing skill-based curriculum (Holt, 2017). Furthermore, in developed countries the percentage of workforce who received formal vocational education were 52 % in United States, 75% in Germany and 96% in South Korea. However, in India it was less than 5 % in 12th Five year Plan period (GoI, 2020).</p> <p>NEP envisages to give exposure for at least 50% of learners undergoing school education to vocational skill-based training by 2025. To make Vocational Training relevant to the present dynamics of the world collaborations are encouraged. For instance, Secondary Schools are supposed to collaborate with it is, Polytechnics, local Industry, and the like to give their students practical exposure. Moreover, Higher educational Institutions are supposed to offer Skill enhancing Vocational Courses by having active collaboration with Industries and Non-Governmental Organisations. In addition to it, HEI's are also supposed to offer short term certificate courses on <i>Lok Vidya</i>/Soft skills. The said courses are to be made available in through Open and Distance Learning (ODL) system.</p>

2.Measures to enhance Teaching Efficacy of Faculties: If today's children are to be regarded as nation's future, then teachers are entrusted with the responsibility of giving shape to that future. Given the importance and gravitas of profession in question along with the potential of creating far reaching externalities, multiple safeguards must be put in place to ensure that our

children receive teaching from genuine faculties who are truly passionate about teaching. Understanding the gravity of situation, NEP 2020 has laid down the following guidelines and initiatives to enhance efficacy and bring in accountability among teaching fraternity:

i) Creating quality Human Resource with a greater focus on Rural Area: Nearly a century ago, Father of our Nation remarked that India lived in villages, when we fast forward to twenty first century, given nearly 65% of our population still reside in rural area, what he told then, holds true even now. Noting the significance of empowering rural areas, NEP has envisaged to provide special merit-based scholarships for students pursuing 4-year integrated Bachelors in Education (B.Ed) programmes in rural areas. It is hoped that this initiative shall be very helpful for female students in securing job in near their place of residence. To further incentivise, well trained faculties to take up teaching in rural schools, NEP has laid down guidelines to provide residence on the school premises along the lines of Kendriya Vidyalaya or increase their housing allowances. Furthermore, Teachers Eligibility Test (TET) shall be designed in keeping with the needs and demands of 21st century so as to ensure quality is not compromised.

ii) Bring in Transparency in Transfers of Teachers: To begin with NEP acknowledges that, frequent transfers of teachers is detrimental to students' learning. To ensure that students don't needlessly suffer, the frequency of Teacher's transfers shall be greatly curtailed. At the same point of time, to accommodate genuine requests, an online computerised system shall be put in place to ensure transparency in the process.

iii) Leveraging Local Resources to Enhance teaching Experience: Educational institutions must ensure that they give maximum exposure to their students. To achieve the said objective, Educational Institutions are encouraged to hire local experts as 'master instructors' to teach various subjects like arts, entrepreneurship, vocational crafts or any other local speciality in which that particular individual may have gained expertise in. Doing so shall not only be beneficial for the students, but it shall also go a long way in preserving and promoting local knowledge and professions.

iv) Continuous Professional Development: To do justice for their professions and stay relevant in their domain, Teachers must be updating themselves on a regular basis. The new policy envisages to create a conducive environment for teachers to achieve the same. Workshops, Seminars, Conferences which are to be organised at both national and international level are going to facilitate teachers to learn latest innovations and advances in their profession. Furthermore, online platforms will be developed to facilitate teachers to share their ideas and best practices. Each Teacher is expected to undergo 50 hours of such continuous professional development programme annually.

Similar modular leadership or management workshops are also to be conducted for School Principals, Headmasters, and the like to improve their leadership and management skills. These leaders are expected to undergo such continuous professional development programmes for 50 hours or more on annual basis.

v) Career Management and Progression: The new policy envisages to put a system in place which promotes efficient teachers who are doing exemplary work. To assess the performance of teachers, multiple parameters like attendance, peer reviews, exemplary achievements in the

field of academia, commitment shown in continuous professional development are to be taken into consideration. Furthermore, outstanding teachers who would have shown exemplary management and leadership skills would be trained to take over school leadership and top management positions relating to academics in Government departments.

vi) Training Special Educators: If Education is to bring about Social Justice, then it has to be inclusive. Keeping in line with Rights of Persons with Disabilities (RPWD) Act 2016, children with disability/ *divyang* are to be provided education in inclusive environment wherein students with or without disability learn together. Such students need specially trained teachers to be sensitive to their problems and facilitate their learning. NEP gives equal emphasis on training teachers to meet the needs and demands of such students.

vii) Structural Changes in Teachers' Education: Provisions are to be made, on one hand to run B.ed as a 4 year integrated programme. On the other hand, there shall also be 1 year B. Ed programmes for those students who have completed 4 year multidisciplinary Bachelors degree in that speciality. The two-year B.Ed. programme which is being offered now will continue in the same format. The syllabi of B. Ed shall be in tune with the guiding principles of NEP 2020. In addition to B. Ed and M.Ed., short term courses shall be offered at Behaviour Information Thought & Emotion Education (BITEs) and District Institute for Education and Training (DIETs) to enhance the efficacy of teachers.

Furthermore, Doctoral students pursuing research will be required to take credit-based courses in teaching pedagogy, writing and communication in their chosen specialisation. Exposure to pedagogical practices is envisaged to make research scholars efficient teachers and communicators. Even if they chose not to pursue teaching after research, being effective communicators is going to pay them lifelong dividends.

3.Measures to enhance the Efficacy and Efficiency of Research: Any nation's economic growth and development is dependent on the quantum of innovation it can produce through it's the strength of its own human capital (Shukla, 2017). Inventions and innovations in the field of engineering, warfare, philosophy, and sciences propelled ancient civilization of Greece, Rome, Mesopotamia, Egypt, Persia, China and India to their Glory days. Ironically lack of invention and innovation saw the downfall of these great civilisations as well. Even in modern times the superpowers of the day like America and European Countries strength lies in their education system which focuses on creating new knowledge and innovative practises. Hence, if India has to reclaim her former glory and effectively face modern challenges like climate change, pollution, food security, national security, maintaining international stability and the like, then India must focus on building reliable knowledge economy. To achieve the same Research and development has a very important role to play. Interestingly, the nations who have world class education, have successfully integrated research and practical application of knowledge to their curriculum. Conversely such conducive environment is more effectively created in multidisciplinary universities.

Noting the importance and relevance of building a sound research base to promote sustainable growth and development of Nation, NEP 2020 has taken the following initiative to promote research and development in the nation:

As of now research in the nation is funded by many of the institutions like University Grants Commission, department of Atomic Energy, department of science and Technology, Indian Council of Agricultural Research, Indian Council of Historical Research and Department of Biotechnology along with various private and philanthropic organisations. According to the new policy, these organisations will still be funding research. However, the NEP, envisions establishment of National Research Foundation which shall coordinate and collaborate with other funding agencies to ensure synergy of purpose and avoid duplication (Roy, 2020).

The focus of NRF will be:

- i) Fund peer reviewed competitive grant proposals across all disciplines.
- ii) Facilitate and mentor and oversee the growth of practical-oriented research in Higher Educational Institutions wherein research is still in nascent stage.
- iii) Act as a liaison between Government, policy makers, industries and researchers, so that researchers work on domains which are practical importance and repercussions on policy formulations.
- iv) Oversee the progress of research along with recognising exemplary research which is being done in the nation.

4. Revamping Regulatory Structure: NEP realizes the heavy-handed nature of the present Regulatory set up which has left much to be desired. Underlining the importance of eliminating conflicts of interests and bringing in transparency and public accountability in the system, NEP has envisaged four vertical bodies to regulate nation's academic infrastructure which would be overseen by a superstructure to ensure collaboration and synergy of action between the vertical regulatory bodies.

The Superstructure which is envisaged by the policy to overlook the operation of the vertical bodies is christened to be the Higher Education Commission of India (HECI).

i) Regulation: The first vertical of HECI shall be National Higher Education Regulatory Council (NHERC). It is envisioned to be a common point regulator for all Higher Educational Institutions across the board except those dealing with medical and legal education. NHERC is designed to perform 'light but tight' regulation. It is going to maintain a public website through which all the information and records that it is going to collect from the higher educational institutions for the purpose of regulation shall be kept for public access. This shall be updated at regular intervals. This shall ensure transparency and accountability in the system. Moreover, if any of the disclosed information from the HEIs are found to be false upon inspection, stringent action shall be taken against those institutions. Furthermore, as an additional safeguard, online reviews from students, including differently abled students shall be collected and uploaded by NHERC on its website. This exercise shall ensure Higher Educational Institutions are held accountable in more ways than one and are doing justice to their responsibility.

ii) Accreditation: The Second vertical of HECI shall be National Accreditation Council which is designed to act as 'Meta Accrediting Body'. In the new system, the purpose of accreditation

is not just evaluating as to whether the Higher Educational Institutions are maintaining an expected level of standards or not, it is designed to be an avenue through which Higher educational Institutions can earn their autonomy within a span of 15 years. In other words, NAC's valuation shall lay out phased benchmarks based on Institutional Developmental Plans (IDPs), basic norms, good governance and outcomes for HEIs will be evaluated on. With greater level of performance in those parameters HEIs can hope to achieve greater degree of self-governance and autonomy. Ultimately, the objective of NAC is to aid in establishing self-governing, accountable and autonomous institutions which maintain high standards in their domain (Balagurusamy, 2020).

iii) Funding: The third vertical of HECI shall be Higher Education Grants Council (HEGC) which is supposed to provide funding for scholarship and implementation of developmental goals for HEIs. HEGC is envisioned to fund HEIs on transparent basis. Disbursement of fund shall be based on evaluating Institutional Developmental Plans laid down by HEIs and the degree of progress made by them in achieving the same. HEGC is also expected to disburse developmental funds on new focus areas and expanding upon relevant research and developmental progress across all the disciplines.

iv) Framing Objectives: It is often said that a journey of thousand miles begins with a single step. However, for a journey to be successful, the traveller must be aware as to where he is going, why he is going and how he is going. The fourth vertical of HECI, General Education Council (GEC), is designed to frame objectives which shall serve as a guiding light for the journey undertaken by Higher Educational Sector. GEC is expected to formulate a National Higher Educational Qualification Framework (NHEQF) which is supposed to collaborate with National Skills Qualification Framework (NSQF) to create a conducive environment for integrating skill based vocational learning in higher education. The main objective of GEC shall be to identify 'graduate attributes' or skills which shall make graduates relevant and ready to be productive assets for themselves and the society.

v) Making Education Affordable for all: NEP envisions Education to be 'a not for profit' venture. In line with its objective the policy desires to curb commercialisation of education. To achieve the same, NEP plans to leverage NHERC and NAC to ensure that masses have access to affordable quality education. In the new regulatory regime, public and private institutions are to be treated on same footing. There shall be transparency in fee determining process. Educational institutions are to be run as 'not for profit' entities. Based on their accreditation status they will be allowed to fix their fees, Furthermore, the institutions will not be allowed to revise their fee structure, once a student has enrolled to a particular course. In addition to it, HEIs are supposed to make fee structure available in public domain. If Educational Institutions are running a surplus, then they are supposed to reinvest the same to further improve educational infrastructure of their respective institutions.

NEP envisages to encourage progressive fee structure in HEIs which are having philanthropic and public-spirited intent. Although NEP fixes upper limit for fee structure, it realises that cost of the same course taught in different institutions may substantially differ based on how it is taught. Hence NEP, makes a provision for different institutions to have different fee structure for the same course based on that Institution's accreditation level. At the same point of time,

none of the institutions would be allowed to charge fees greater than the upper limit. Hence institutions are allowed to fix their fees with certain degree of autonomy which would be subject to overall regulation. All in all, the fee determining mechanism tries to strike a delicate balance between recovery of cost and their responsibility of fulfilling social obligations for HEIs

vi) Effective Governance and Leadership for Higher Educational institutions: NEP strongly emphasises that to build world Class Institutions in India, we need to select proven meritorious leaders who have commitment to constitutional values and towards betterment of society. To achieve the same after getting accredited from relevant agency, the concerned Higher Educational Institution must appoint Board of Governors (BoG). BoG shall comprise of a group of eminent, socially responsible and proven experts with a strong sense of commitment for promoting institution's excellence. In order remove any conflict of interest with earlier legislations, NEP advises to promulgate an overarching legislation which shall supersede all the contravening provisions of earlier legislations dealing with constitution, appointment, functioning and other rules and regulation concerning BoG. It shall be the responsibility of BoG to carry out impartial merit-based appointment to various positions by constituting Eminent Expert Committee (EEC). It is advised that measures should also be put in place to parallelly train next generation of leaders to take place of BoG's current leadership when time comes. The ultimate agenda behind putting this system in place is to create self-governing autonomous Higher educational Institutions which can educate students and make them assets to both our society and nation.

5. Other Focus Areas of National Education Policy: From the onset the focus of National Education Policy has been to ensure access, equity, quality, affordability and accountability in Educational Sector which is in line with the objectives set by "2030 Agenda for sustainable Development" (Panditrao & Panditrao, 2020) . In keeping with the objective of NEP, the other prominent focus areas of NEP are as follows:

i) Professional Education: George Akerlof remarks 'Cause of anything is everything.' NEP realises that Professionals in any field cannot work in isolation. As they are part of society, they are bound to be influenced by all the factors governing society. Hence to do justice to the complex workplace that the graduates shall be exposed to, NEP gives emphasis on moving from stand alone universities to Multi-disciplinary Universities so that graduates are able to interrelate the cause and consequences of things unfolding before them and take appropriate measures to address the same.

In line with multidisciplinary spirit important guidelines issued by NEP are as follows:

a) Agricultural Education must be integrated with allied sciences so as to create skilled work force who are adept in using local knowledge, traditional knowledge and emerging technologies to address the prominent challenges and problems that the society shall be facing in foreseeable future.

b) Legal Education must adhere to global standards and must be in line with justice-social, economic and political as propounded by Indian constitutional ethos. Furthermore, NEP

suggests that Legal Education must be provided in English and concerned regional language of the state for future lawyers and judges to make them more sensitive towards the masses.

c) NEP recognises that people exercise pluralistic choice in health care. Hence, to make healthcare professional more sensitive to the needs and demands of society, new policy gives emphasis on the need of making Healthcare Education system more integrated. In the new system Allopathic students shall be having basic knowledge of AYUSH medicine and vice versa.

d) With advent of new millennia coupled with digital revolution, the differentiating line between technical and non-technical subjects are starting to blur. Recognising interlinkages between genomic study, biotechnology, neuroscience, nano technology, big data analytics and data science, NEP envisions to promote technical education through multidisciplinary approach (Ferrao, 2020).

ii) Adult Education: Many studies have already established strong correlation between literacy and GDP (Rahman, 2011; Coulombe et al., 2006) . As one of the prime objectives of NEP is to ensure inclusivity in education, adult literacy had to be included. Given, the increasing penetration of technology in all the domains of society, adult education is necessary to bring in inclusive development keeping in line with natural law of justice. To achieve the objective NEP seeks to leverage specialised wing of NCERT to create syllabus for adult education. Curriculum for Adult Education is to be designed to cover the following aspects:

a) Foundational literacy and numeracy

b) Critical Life Skills: which includes Digital Literacy, Financial Literacy, Family Welfare, Health Care, Child Care and Commercial Skills.

c) Vocational Skills Development: which would help the individual to gain local employment.

d) Basic Education: including Preparatory, Middle and Secondary Stage equivalent.

e) Continuing Education: through which the concerned adult can pursue education in science, arts, music, sports and recreation.

Campuses of Educational Institutions after working hours and weekends along with public libraries are planned to be leveraged for imparting adult education. As the learners in case of adult education are matured individuals, instructors or mentor shall be specially trained by National, State and District level resource building institutions. To further the cause, NEP also plans to leverage faculties working in HEIs for educating adults.

iii) Promoting Indian Languages, Art and Culture: NEP recognises the importance of culture in promoting one's self esteem and sense of identity. Furthermore, it also recognises the fact that culture of people is encased in their languages. It is knowledge of the language which truly helps us to understand and appreciate art, literature and music through which legacy of a culture manifests. Unfortunately, in past 50 years India has lost over 220 of her languages (Dwivedi & Kar, 2017). Moreover, UNESCO has declared 197 of Indian languages to be 'endangered'. Recognising the importance of language in preserving culture, NEP has

envisaged to undertake the following measures to safeguard and promote the multicultural heritage of India:

- a) Learning and Teaching of Indian languages are to be integrated in Academic Curricula.
- b) Scholarships to be awarded for people across all ages, who wish to study Indian art, languages and culture.
- c) Academies are to be established for each of 22 languages mentioned in the 8th schedule of the constitution which would be led by eminent scholars, renowned writers and knowledgeable speakers to update and enrich the vocabulary of the concerned language on regular basis.
- d) India is a multicultural nation. To enable people from various regions to understand and appreciate each other's culture, Indian Institute of Translation and Interpretation (IITI) to be established. IITI would leverage technology and collaborate with other research institutes to translate quality learning materials and literature of various languages, with a focus on promoting all Indian languages. In the long run IITI is envisioned to have multiple regional centres which would be present, including in HEIs.
- e) Sanskrit Universities are to be transformed into multidisciplinary universities which would facilitate in studying Nation's culture, heritage, and literature along with Sanskrit. Furthermore, 4 year integrated multidisciplinary B.Ed. programmes to be designed which would award a dual degree in Education and Sanskrit. Along with Sanskrit, measures are also to be put in place to establish National Institute(s) for Pali, Persian and Prakrit in University campus,

iv) Integrating Technology in Teaching Learning Pedagogy: NEP recognises the manifold positive externalities which could be generated by leveraging Information Communication technology to enhance the quality and efficacy of teaching learning experience. At the same point of time, NEP also understands that the implementation of the same in Indian context is akin to moving into unknown territory. So, the measures envisioned by NEP to carefully implement the same are as follows:

- a) *Pilot studies:* Pilot studies are to be conducted by eminent organisations and research institutes like NETF, CIET, IGNOU, NITs, IITs etc to understand the pros and cons of integrating technology in learning. In addition to it constant feedback of all stakeholders are to be taken into account while framing the final policy.
- b) *Building Necessary Digital Infrastructure:* To leverage digital technology, corresponding digital infrastructure is a mandatory requirement. NEP suggests the government to make the necessary investment in digital infrastructure to bridge the gap.
- c) *Leveraging Online Learning Portals:* Existing e-learning portals like DIKSHA and SWAYAM, SWAYAMPRAKASHA are to be transformed into learning friendly two-way platform to facilitate interactive learning among teachers and students.
- d) *Content creation and dissemination:* Measures to be put in place to ensure that e-learning materials are made available in native languages for students. Furthermore, a digital repository to be created wherein content related to creation of coursework, simulated learning, and Augmented learning systems shall be stored which could be accessed by the academia. To

understand the utility of the system for academia a rating mechanism would also be inbuilt in the repository. Most interesting aspect of the NEP in this regard is that the policy aims to make learning fun for students.

e) *Measures to bridge the digital divide in short run:* NEP recognises the fact that not all students shall be having the digital devices to access the digital content. To circumvent the problem, the new policy envisages to leverage the digital devices like Television, Radio, satellite channels which are already in vogue to transmit the learning content 24/7.

f) *Incentivising Teachers to adopt blended learning:* Teachers who are good in traditional mode of teaching may not be equally efficient in online mode. Moreover, NEP has envisioned to shift the teaching learning pedagogy from teacher centric model to learner centric model. To accustom teachers to new norm, the new policy envisages to extensively train the faculty in learner-centric pedagogy.

g) *Online Assessment:* When emphasis is laid on integrating online learning with traditional mode of learning, online assessment cannot be ignored. Online assessment has its own inherent opportunities, challenges and limitations. NEP proposes to leverage National Assessment Centre (PARAKH), NTA, School Boards and other eminent organisations to design a comprehensive framework of online assessment for testing as to whether the learner has gained relevant skills to meet modern demands of the new century.

h) *Laying down Standards:* After understanding the opportunities and challenges of introducing e-learning in Indian backdrop, NEP envisages National Educational Technology Forum (NETF) along with other suitable organisations to lay down guidelines and standards for implementing e-learning pedagogy at ground level.

6. Funding: Financing plays a crucial role to manifest any vision to reality. Noting that, public expenditure on education in India with centre and state combined is 4.43 % of GDP (2017-18), NEP suggests the government must increase its expenditure on education to 6% of GDP. Noting that change to truly be successful must require active participation and involvement from society, NEP has suggested incentives to actively encourage private philanthropic activity in educational sector.

7. Implementation: Any policy is only as good as how well it is implemented. Recognising concurrent nature of Education in constitution along with, the magnitude and complexity of the task at hand NEP underlines the fact that, the policy can not be implemented in one go and shall take better part of 2 decades to execute. To systematically implement the policy, the NEP underscores that, there must be synchronised and systematic effort between various bodies including Union and State Governments, education related ministries, Central Advisory Board of Education along with NCERT, SCERTs, HEIs and school boards. Furthermore, given the interlinkages between the various initiatives of the policy, NEP suggests that all the aspects of policy must be implemented wholistically so as to maximise the efficiency and effectiveness of the initiative.

Major Innovations Introduced by NEP 2020

1. Overhauling School education: As of now, children education starts from 6 years with the aid of 10+2+3+2 model. However, the new policy envisions to start children education from 3 years with 5+3+3+4+4+1 model.

2. Changing the Nature of Learning: NEP envisions to revamp the teacher centric learning model to student centric learning model. To achieve the same, it lays emphasis on leveraging Information Communication Technology and promoting blended learning.

3. Making education wholistic fun and more engaging: Recognising education must result in wholistic development of children by improving their cognitive, reasoning, and psycho motor capabilities, NEP envisions to create a conducive environment to achieve the same. Furthermore, to remove stereotypical notions in society new policy has removed hard lined distinctions between vocational and academic courses, curricular and extracurricular activities and between science, arts and commerce streams.

4. Vocational Training: Although previous policies had recognised the importance and need for integrating vocational training, NEP 2020 has gone that extra mile to formally integrate skill based vocational training in formal curriculum. Vocational training coupled with multiple entries and exit is going to make the education more wholistic for students (Aiyappa, 2020). In fact, NEP 2020 envisages to make at least 50 percent of learners undergoing school education to get exposed to skill based vocational courses by 2025.

5. Multidisciplinary Focus: NEP 2020 recognises that cause of anything is everything. Hence any one discipline in isolation cannot give solution to the complex nature of problems and challenges which are arising in the society. Hence, to effectively tackle the same, NEP focuses on implementing Multidisciplinary approach to learning.

6. Overhauling Regulatory Structure: Underlining the importance of eliminating conflicts of interests and bringing in transparency and accountability in the process of funding, regulation, accreditation and framing objectives, NEP has envisaged four vertical bodies to perform the aforementioned functions. They would in turn be overseen by a superstructure to ensure collaboration and synergy of action exists between the vertical regulatory bodies.

7. Providing Autonomy for HEIs: In the present state of affairs autonomy was a distant dream for many of the Higher Educational Institutions. New policy focuses on providing autonomy to Higher Educational Institutions based on their level of accreditation which would in turn be function of their efficiency.

8. Inviting Top 100 Universities: To make quality education more affordable and instil a spirit of competition in education sector, NEP has allowed top 100 universities to open educational institutions in India.

9. Adult Education: In line with the spirit of promoting 'education for all' NEP 2020 has envisioned to a formalised structural setup to systematically provide adult education with a commendable objective of achieving 100 % literacy rate in India.

Possible Impediments in Implementing NEP 2020 Based on Predictive Analysis

1. Cultural Barriers: NEP 2020 envisages to change the education system from teacher centric model to learner centric model. It is true that the model has been very much successful in western countries. However, renaissance had imbibed the culture of questioning anything and everything in western setup which eventually percolated to their education system as well. However, in India the social and political setup doesn't encourage questioning of established norms. That being the case, trying to implement such a radical idea in educational sector alone is going to be a challenging affair.

2. Training Teachers in Blended Learning Model: According to recent studies it has been found that experienced faculty find effectively using newer digital tools cumbersome (Chetan et al., 2020). That being the case implementing radical new structure with existing human resource is going to be challenging.

3. Maintaining Accountability: The new system envisages to create an environment which promotes efficient teachers, particularly in Government system. The measure as noble as it may seem doesn't seem to be wholistic in nature. In the present set up, if a faculty gets into government institution on permanent basis, then his job is secure independent of his or her performance. NEP 2020 doesn't explicitly highlight the corrective measures which are to be enforced to ensure accountability among irresponsible faculty.

4. Lobbies: NEP 2020 envisages to bring in merit-based system to appoint Board of Governors, leaders and faculties in educational sector. However, appointments can never happen in isolation (Kapur and Mehta, 2008), particularly in a democratic set up like India. Education sector can run on meritocracy only when all the other government machineries have inculcated meritocracy in their system. Hoping to inculcate meritocracy in any one sector in isolation seems to be a farfetched initiative.

5. Transforming Nature of Educational sector: NEP 2020 hopes to transform educational sector from 'profit oriented' enterprise to 'service oriented' enterprise which would be accessible to all. At the same point of time, noting the expenses involved, the new policy gives lee way for different institutions to charge different fees based on their level of accreditation, provided that their fee structure is under the upper limit fixed by the regulatory authorities. Noble as the idea may be, in present dynamics killing profit initiative may not be conducive to attract the best players in the enterprise.

6. Unaddressed Dualism: NEP 2020 envisages to invite top 100 universities to establish their branches in India. On one hand, this initiative is hoped to make international level education affordable to masses and on the other hand, it is hoped that Indian Universities shall raise their game when faced with international competition (Almeida, 2020).

If we consider the present state of affairs, there are some elite institutions in India like IITs, IIMs, IISc and the like. However, our state universities which are serving the needs of masses doesn't seem to have been inspired to raise their game when faced with domestic elite institutions. Furthermore, the existing elite institutions are only serving the interests of few of the chosen elite in India. If past trend is anything to go by, hoping elite institutions would make education affordable to masses seems to be farfetched.

7. Overhauling of Exams: To make education more fun and reduce the level of stress and anxiety among students, NEP 2020 desires to revamp the existing exam structure at various levels, which does seem to be the right thing to do. However, when we observe the present state of affairs, feasibility of revamping the exam structure seems to be questionable on two accounts:

First, NEP has mentioned that students will be facing exams in 3rd, 5th and 8th standard, It is not clear as to annual exams will be conducted from 1st standard to 8th standard. If annual exam from 1st to 8th standard is to be scrapped, it may result in the following negative externalities due to the following reasons: On one hand, young children lack maturity to understand the importance of learning. On the other, if they are not adept in understanding the basics, then it would be very difficult for them to cope up with advanced concepts. Annual exams, particularly at this stage, despite its limitations brings in a sense of seriousness and accomplishment for children which drives them to try to learn basics with a certain degree of seriousness. Even with annual exam system, according to ASER report 2016, proportion of class V children who could read class II level text had fallen to 47.8% in 2016 from 48.1 % in 2014. If the students have no fear of annual exam, particularly at this tender age, things may take a turn for worse.

Second, NEP 2020 envisions to conduct one common entrance exam for admission in undergraduate and post graduate courses. Although at superficial level it does seem to be fair, when we look into details, second thoughts are bound to arise due to the following reasons. Common entrance exam for UG and PG courses would be fair only if students receive uniform education at previous level. However, ensuring uniform quality of education across all school boards is going to be a daunting affair.

In addition to it, entrance exam for graduate admissions is going to foster competition and growth of coaching institutes which may create more stress for the students. As it is, according to NCRB in 28 students are committing suicides in 24 hours (Shuvabrata G.,2020).

8. Lack of Specialisation: NEP focuses on giving the students freedom to choose at pre university level. In the previous system, there was a clear-cut path for the student to follow which facilitated specialisation. However, new system has the potential of creating confusion among students (Joshi et al., 2021). Given dynamic nature of job opportunities, if students are allowed to choose combinations without proper guidance, it may be detrimental for them in the long run.

9. Issues with uniformity: The new policy seems to follow top-down approach. Although, there are enough feedback mechanisms which are put in place to constantly take the feedback of all the stakeholders involved, trying to construct a uniform academic structure and curricula for a diverse and a multicultural country like India doesn't seem to do justice. Inculcating nationalism along with doing justice to regional legacy is going to be a daunting task for framers and implementors of the policy.

10. Lack of Adequate Infrastructural Facility: In India HEIs can be classified under 3 categories. Central universities which receive substantial funding from Central Government. State funded Universities which receive relatively less funds as compared to central universities and Private funded Universities which are mostly run for profit motive (Jha and Parvati, 2020).

When it comes to School boards, central boards are well funded and run by central government. When it comes to state boards which can cater to masses, most of them lack adequate infrastructure and Private schools cater to the needs of select few who have the ability to pay. In this backdrop, NEP has envisioned to introduce blended learning in curricula. Two of the prominent problems in this setting are, most of the students don't have access to digital gadgets. Moreover, even when the students have access to digital gadgets, they lack access to complementary infrastructure like internet and electricity to effectively utilise the same (Chetan and Rangappa, 2021).

Conclusion

National Education Policy was the need of the hour for a nation entering into new century and faced with disruptive challenges of modern age. On the outset NEP 2020 seems to be a very progressive document with an intention to revamp archaic educational infrastructure to create a unified, equitable, accountable and accessible educational system which would bestow our youth with skillset required to thrive and flourish in modern times. To achieve the same, NEP lays emphasis on transforming teacher centric education to learner centric education. To further facilitate the process, it aims to leverage Information Communication Technology. Noting that any change in society, requires active support and participation of the society, it focuses on creating a conducive environment to encourage societal minded philanthropic private institutions to play an active role in nation's sustainable growth and development. Further it aims to create a 'light but tight' regulatory system which shall ultimately promote self-sustaining autonomous institutions which focus on excelling in their respective domains. In addition to that, to ensure teachers do justice to their task at hand, NEP lays emphasis on regular training of teachers through Continuous professional development programmes. As good as a policy may be, its ultimate success depends upon how well it is implemented and to what extent it is accepted by the society. Although a uniform structure would do well to raise standards and instil a sense of pride and identity among learners, caution must be taken as to not ignore regional sentiments (Maurya, A & Ahmed., 2020). India is a multicultural, multi lingual and multifaceted nation having variety of culture and legacies. Thus while implementing NEP as a unified model, a modus operandi must be put in place to do justice to regional sentiments as well. None of the macroeconomic policies can be implemented in isolation. Success of NEP not only depends upon how well it is going to be integrated with other complementary initiatives like 'Make in India' , 'Digital India', 'Skill India' and the like (Kurien and Chandramana, 2020), its success is also going to be dictated by the extent of self-correction it can bring within the system by taking constant feedback of all the stakeholders involved. Furthermore, hoping to bring in transparency and accountability in one part of the system without taking measures to assure the same in other parts of the system may ultimately prove to be an unsuccessful venture.

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